

Statistical Similarities Between Quantum Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics in the Case of the Oscillator

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 12, 2018

Both quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics predict the same momentum and spatial density forms for the solution of an oscillator. In the case of quantum mechanics, the ground state is considered. One may ask whether this is a coincidence, and if not, why two seemingly different theories should lead to the same result for the oscillator case. We argue in this note that it is the form of the conservation equation of the oscillator which leads to x and p having the same probability distribution. Furthermore, given that both quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics are of a statistical nature, one may inquire into the actual nature of the statistics being used, the meaning behind averages being used. For example, the classical deterministic solution of an oscillator can be written in statistical terms by removing time dependence and using $\text{density} = dx/v$. This does not mean, however, that the actual physical motion is no longer deterministic. In addition, we try to argue that quantum mechanics may be a more detailed statistical model including dynamics which satisfies the more static statistical result of spatial density for classical statistical mechanics.

Statistical Properties of the Oscillator

The harmonic oscillator conservation of energy equation can be written as:

$.5p^2/m + .5k x^2 = E$ where E is the energy. The point we wish to make is that p and x appear in exactly the same manner. Thus, it is argued that any statistical distribution of p should be the same for x . Thus, classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics, both being statistical theories should have this property. This is in fact the case;

Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics, it seems that the driving idea is that numerous particles scatter in such a way as to maintain a resonance with the probability for a particular p being proportional to $\exp(-.5p^2/mT)$. This result holds both for a dense gas with many interparticle collisions or for a sparse gas in which collisions are with a wall that is at temperature T . In such a gas, it is the wall which drives the temperature equilibrium.

Let us examine the sparse gas case in one dimension with an oscillator potential. In such a case, a particle starts with velocity v at one wall, moves in a deterministic manner along the potential and then at the second wall receives a different velocity in the backward direction as determined statistically by the wall which is at temperature T . Let us imagine for the sake of argument that the potential has a value of 0 at the first wall, then the relative probabilities for v are $\exp(-.5v^2/T)$. As the particles move in a deterministic manner in the oscillator potential, the

kinetic energy of each will change, but the relative probability will not. In fact, for a given v_1 the total energy at the first wall is $.5m v_1^2$ which equals $.5mv^2 + V(x)$ at any point so the probability can be written as $\exp(-(.5mv^2 + V(x))/T)$. This equation will hold for each particle, but particles with different speeds will be at different positions at a given time. If one averages over v , however, one obtains a spatial density of $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. The particles, however, contribute to this density at different times. Thus, the average seems to be a little misleading because time dependence has been removed in the dilute gas case, although it is still an average. Thus, it seems that in the dilute gas of classical statistical mechanics, the statistical nature of statistical mechanics removes deterministic motion which is actually occurring when the gas is not colliding with the walls. The particles with different speeds reach a particular point x at different times, nevertheless if one is not concerned with position at a particular time, then the statistical average applies. The point argued seems to be that one has to be very careful as to the meaning of the average. As pointed out, one can describe the deterministic motion of a classical oscillator in a statistical manner by writing density = dx/v as done in (1). Time information is removed in such a picture as is the deterministic nature of actual motion. Physically, of course, a very specific pattern of motion is occurring. Thus, one must be very careful in the interpretation of the statistical model, as it is the underlying deterministic motion which is reality.

Thus, analysis of a dilute gas seems to agree with the classical statistical mechanical result that the velocity distribution is $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ and the spatial $\exp(-.5kx^2/T)$, although one has to be careful in interpreting the spatial density in terms of microscopic motion.

Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, it is argued that there is a relationship between position and momentum. This appears in the Heisenberg uncertainty relationship between Δx and Δp , but also in the wavefunction. The wavefunction is a function of x , yet its Fourier series yields probabilities for having particular values of momentum. In general, a Fourier series is simply a mathematical expansion and does not give dynamical information as it does in quantum mechanics. Thus, quantum mechanics is a very specific kind of statistical theory. One may write:

$$W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \sin(px)$$

Now, it is possible to set $f(p) = \exp(-p^2/a)$ where a is some constant. This would give a momentum probability distribution equal to that found in classical statistical mechanics. Given that $p^2/2m + kx^2/2 = E$, one would expect that the spatial density should be a Gaussian in x . Thus, $W(x)$, the wavefunction should be a Gaussian in x , because spatial density is $W(x)W(x)$ for a real wavefunction. This means that the Fourier transform of $\exp(-ap^2)$ should convert into the same function, which is exactly what happens in the case of the oscillator. (It should be noted that when solving the Schrodinger equation for the oscillator, the solutions involving Hermite polynomials retain this property (2)). The interesting point in quantum mechanics is that one deals with a wavefunction $W(x)$ instead of dealing directly with a spatial density. It seems that the wavefunction contains dynamics which disappear in the more static

statistical object, spatial density. It is interesting that for the oscillator case, quantum mechanics seems to give a more detailed solution, which is still a solution of the classical statistical mechanical results for the oscillator. The oscillator seems to be the only case where this agreement occurs because statistical mechanics dictates that the momentum distribution be a Gaussian, and the Fourier transform in quantum mechanics dictates that for a Gaussian momentum distribution, the spatial wavefunction must also be a Gaussian. It was noted in (3), that quantum mechanics could be thought of as giving $P(p/x)$, i.e. spatial dependent values for the probability of a given momentum. In classical statistical mechanics one also deals with $P(p/x)$ because the probability to have a given p changes as one moves from one point in the potential to another. In the case of quantum mechanics, it was argued in (4), that there is physical meaning associated with the $\sin(px)$ term. In particular, it was suggested that a quantum particle undergoes zitterbewegung and so is not a point particle with a specific velocity at a specific point in space. In fact, it was argued that a quantum particle placed in a potential would lead to many plane waves with different momentum values being generated in such a way that the average kinetic energy at a point would satisfy a conservation of energy equation i.e.:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m f(p) \sin(px)]/W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Here, $W(x)$ the wavefunction, acts as a normalization constant which is dependent on position. It was also argued that cycling was occurring (4).

Classical Statistical Mechanics and a Dense Gas

In the case of statistical mechanics, one may wonder if the quantum mechanical wavefunction approach of quantum mechanics may have any relevance. For quantum mechanics, it was argued that a particle has zitterbewegung and can be modeled by $\sin(px)$. This $\sin(px)$ exists even when the potential disappears (e.g. for a quantum particle bouncing between two walls) and so seems to be associated with the physical nature of a quantum particle. In classical statistical mechanics, a particle exists at a point and has a well defined velocity at such a point. Thus, at first glance the two seem to be inconsistent. In the classical statistical mechanics of a dense gas, one may, however, try to argue that the thermalization process for an oscillator tries to establish each momentum p at each point in space with the probability of $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. For an oscillator, space and momentum have the same form in the conservation of energy equation, so one might guess that this thermalization might be periodic with an argument px , which treats p and x equally. It was argued in (5), that $\sin(px)$ is a periodic solution which might be applicable as it has certain properties regarding probability flow. One might think of thermalized particles being added periodically at points in space and then have these give an average kinetic energy ((1)). There would then be a kind of underlying wave type motion which is not visible in the averaging used to calculate the spatial density.

Thus, it might be possible that the quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ for an oscillator has meaning even a classical statistical mechanical case. Even if it does not apply to a dense gas, it might apply to other classical phenomena, as it is argued that it is a certain type of statistical model.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is argued that the similarity of the momentum and spatial probability distributions for an oscillator in both classical statistical mechanics and the ground state of quantum mechanics is not an accident. The conservation of energy equation for an oscillator treats the variable p momentum and x position in the same manner and so one, it seems, can expect identical distributions for each regardless of the statistical theory. If the momentum distribution for classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics is the same, it then follows that the spatial distribution should likewise be the same. This is the case for the oscillator (for the ground state quantum mechanical solution). It is further argued that the quantum mechanical wavefunction approach for the ground state oscillator may be a more detailed statistical solution which satisfies the less detailed classical statistical mechanical results for spatial density. The wavefunction contains dynamics, it seems, and such dynamics may also apply to classical systems with an oscillator potential.

References

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